

Problems Facing EFL Students in Practicum Courses at Palestinian Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: February 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: May 02, 2020</p> <hr/> <p><i>Keywords</i></p> <p>Academic supervisor Cooperative teacher Cooperative school Practicum Student teacher</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3785175</p>	<p><i>This study aims at identifying problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities. The study used a proportional stratified random sample consisted of EFL students in practicum courses in the second semester of the academic year (2018-2019). Students' sample consisted of 25 males and 117 females. The researchers designed a questionnaire and a semi-structured interview to collect data. The questionnaire consisted of six domains with 56 items. The selected five universities were Hebron University, Bethlehem University, An-Najah National University, Birzeit University, and Al-Quds Open University. The results of the study showed that the total degree of the problems facing EFL students during their practicum courses at Palestinian universities was medium. They also showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the subjects' responses on the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender, cumulative average or university. There were statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in the practicum courses due to the university concerning problems related to the academic supervisor.</i></p>

Introduction

During the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, the English language has been used as the first international communication instrument. Studies and researches nowadays deal with many various issues in English language teaching. The quality of education cannot be taught without the presence of a responsible and academically and practically qualified teacher in schools. Thus the teacher plays a very important role in the process of learning and teaching in the past and the present. The teachers' role goes beyond that to the whole educational process, and thus to the process of socialization. Hence, the status of the teacher among nations was high and great.

Kawaldeh and Ahmida (2010) stated that recent developments in educational systems emphasize the role of educational institutions in developing and improving teacher training programs. To achieve desired objectives, attention should focus on preparing the teacher for the actual life that makes this preparation specialized, professional and scientific through integrated dimensions that aim to develop and reform the education outcomes.

Yousef and Fauzi (2012) stated that to provide teachers a lot of scientific skills, they need to be engaged in practical training programs. In Palestine, it has been realized that student teachers' training is a necessary stage to well prepare EFL teachers for authentic practice. Student teachers should acquire the necessary experiences and requirements to carry out their duties in the teaching process.

The norms of Salutations in the language, giving an overview of use in helping us to understand mono-cultural and cross-cultural communication in and through English in Britain, as well as giving an overview to ESOL teachers and students of the cultural settings of British salutations, leading to mutual understanding (Ahd Hassan, 2020)

Generally speaking, this study aims to identify the problems that face the EFL student teacher in practicum courses at Palestinian universities. It is hoped that this study will come up with some recommendations that highlight the design of practicum courses according to the student-teachers' needs. To help teachers acquire

professional and behavioral competencies, they need to successfully perform the educational tasks in classrooms.

Statement of the problem

Practicum can be considered as the true field that reveals the extent of awareness, knowledge and actual practice of teachers concerning the various learning strategies that EFL students study at universities. About many previous studies, the researchers found that many problems are encountering EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities. Leaving these problems without being investigated creates obstacles in the face of student teachers and makes them suffer in the future during the period of practicing teaching as official teachers. So, it is of paramount importance to focus more on the practical training for EFL student teachers.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to investigate the following objectives:

1. Identifying the problems that face EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian Universities.
2. Identifying whether there are differences between participants' responses due to gender, cumulative average, and university.

Significance of the study

EFL students at Palestinian universities have a real opportunity to acquire teaching experiences in reality at Palestinian schools through practicum courses. This is the only chance offered to EFL students to practice in reality all the theoretical materials learned and studied throughout the four years spent at universities. In addition to the short period of practice, students face many other problems while meeting the requirements of the practicum courses. The researchers think that it is so important for the officials in Palestinian universities and those in the Ministry of Education to be introduced to these problems and then to overcome them. Student teachers themselves might get benefit from this study as they become more aware of the obstacles that face their classmates. Hosting schools might be better prepared in the future. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this study is one of the rare studies addressing EFL students' problems faced in practicum courses in Palestine.

Questions of the study

The study tries to answer the following questions:

1. What is the degree of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities?
2. Are there differences in arithmetic means among EFL students' responses regarding the problems they face in their practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the variables of the study (gender, cumulative average, university)?

From the second question, the following three hypotheses were formed:

The First null hypothesis (H01-1): There are no statistically significant differences at $(\alpha \leq 0.05)$ between the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender.

The second null hypothesis (H01-2): There are no statistically significant differences at $(\alpha \leq 0.05)$ between the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to cumulative average.

The third null hypothesis (H01-3): There are no statistically significant differences at $(\alpha \leq 0.05)$ between the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to university variable.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

(Hinkel, 2005:22) stated that practicum education is models of supervision, observations of teaching, reflective teaching and action research. Before that, the concentration had been on supplying teachers with practical classroom skills through pre-service training courses, which were typically short and presented by teacher training agencies.

AL-Agha (2000) clarified that teacher preparation is an ongoing process and needs to be developed to keep the pace of the progress as long as there is an existing educational process. Learners need someone to

prepare, guide, advice and to take their hands in the right way. What distinguishes the preparation process of the student teachers is that it is a regenerate, renewed and developed because it is associated with human education.

Chen, et.al (2008) mentioned that Practical education is an important and necessary stage in the preparation of teachers. It is the period in which students are allowed to prepare theoretical, educational and administrative tasks that help them to gain experience and teaching requirements under the supervision and guidance of university supervisors and cooperating school.

Practicum courses help students to put learning into practice. The trainees should have the opportunity to engage in self-reflection and evaluation to identify the areas of strengths and weaknesses of the training program (Farrah, 2019).

Practicum Education Sections

According to (Merhi and Moustafa, 2014:10) who clarified that practical education in universities consists of two important sections: the theoretical section and the practical section. Both of them are essential for the student-teacher during the practicum training offered in all Palestinian universities.

The first section is the theoretical side that aims to prepare students for the practical side in the cooperative schools. The trainees are evaluated in this section through written exams.

The second section is the practical side in which all student teachers practice teaching in classrooms.

Stages of Practicum Education

Barahmeh (2016) stated that the practicum courses pass in three stages:

1-Observation stage: In this stage, the trainees' should spend their period of training at the cooperative schools where they have the opportunity to observe the school rules and environment. They attend classes with the actual teacher in these schools to know the practices and activities inside and outside classes.

2- Participation stage: The student teachers spend weeks practicing educational activities, experiences, and tasks inside and outside the classroom. In this stage, it is expected from them to participate in school committees, activities, and tasks. They also need to conduct and write lesson plans as well as to partial teaching with the help and support of the cooperative teacher. Academic supervisors visit the student's trainees to offer orientation, advice, ideas, and encouragement.

3- Evaluation stage: The academic supervisors visit student teachers at least two times during the training period. In the first visit, the supervisor provides support and feedback, observes and checks teaching aids and lesson planning. In the second visit, the academic supervisor evaluates the student teachers' performance and gives grades. The major element in this process is the portfolio. Each student teacher should provide a portfolio on the teaching aids, CDs, charts, daily diaries, and lesson planning.

Practicum at Palestinian university

All Palestinian universities offer no less than two practicum courses that are closely related to the field of the students. They aim at introducing students to methods of teaching, lesson planning, classroom management, classroom observation, usage of instructional materials, blended learning, etc. Student teachers are usually sent to hosting schools to observe and experience English language teaching and learning and then to practice teaching in the real context. Orientation is the first step, then students are to spend 5 hours per week in hosting schools. The total hours learners need to spend at schools should be no less than 60 hours of school work. Two field visits are usually conducted to guide and evaluate students' demonstrations. The first visit is for guidance and support while the second one for evaluation. After each field visit students either will individually meet the course instructor on an appointed schedule to receive feedback on their classroom teaching practices, or have their feedback on the spot.

Related Studies

Farrah (2019) conducted a study that aimed to analyze the experiences and perceptions of a group of MA students regarding an MA TEFL practicum course at Hebron University during the second semester of the academic year 2015\2016. The participants of the study were 12 MATEFL students enrolled in a practicum course. Reflective journals were used for data collection. The results of the study indicated that the participants benefited from the various components of the practicum course during their experience through micro-teaching, classroom observation, lesson planning, reflective practice, class management in addition to practical.

Alamri (2018) investigated the perceptions of English as a foreign language (EFL) pre-service teachers towards the challenges they face in teaching experience during the practicum period. The sample of the study consisted of 35 Saudi EFL female pre-service teachers in the education diploma program (EDP) attending teaching practicum course at Taibh University, Saudi Arabia. Results of the perceptions of EFL pre-service teachers regarding classroom teaching skills were between highly and moderately to low challenging.

Moussaid and Zerhouni (2017) implemented a study to identify the problems of pre-service teachers during the practicum. It also aimed to explore the most frequent problems of a cohort of English as a foreign language. The sample of the study consisted of 60 high school EFL teacher trainees (aged from 22 to 36) enrolled in a year-long teacher training program. Results of the study showed that an in-depth content analysis of post-lesson written reflections (n=1511) mentor feedback (n=1624) and end of each practicum report (n=337) reveal 23 frequent problems with teaching methodology, class control, and time management as the top concerns. Besides, results also indicated that the trainees' development seems to go through five distinct stages: the five stages conceptual model of trainees' development, self-establishment stage, discrete teaching stage, holistic teaching stage, learner-focused teaching stage and initiation stage.

Koross (2016) conducted a study to identify the student teachers' experiences during teaching practice and its impact on their perception of the teaching profession. The sample of the study consisted of third-year student teachers at the University of Eldoret who had done teaching practice. To collect data, a survey design was used and a quantitative questionnaire was administered on 100 student teachers. Results of the study indicated that the students' experiences had an impact on their perception of the teaching profession and they did experience challenges during their teaching practice.

Furthermore, Barahmeh (2016) investigated the sources of EFL student teachers' anxiety during their practicum experience. Data were collected through student teachers' daily diaries and discussions among the student teachers and their university supervisors during the weekly meeting. The sample of the study consisted of all the 22 student teachers from the Arab American University. The researcher developed diaries for all 22 student teachers during their teaching practicum. Results showed that student teachers benefited a lot through having a more fruitful experience. The findings also showed that EFL student teachers have suffered from several sources of anxiety.

Ruba and Tanni (2016) implemented a study to investigate the reality of teaching practical courses at An-Najah national university and AL-Quds Open University from TEFL student teachers' perspectives. A questionnaire was developed for data collection. The results of the study showed that there were no statistical differences between the subjects' responses due to gender, cumulative average, and university. Furthermore, it showed that the reality of the practicum course in both universities was not wishful.

Methods and procedures

Sample of the study

A proportional stratified random sample was chosen from a population of 224 students. It consisted of (142) EFL students distributed into (25) males and (117) females.

Instrumentation

Questionnaire

The researchers used a six- domain questionnaire to collect data on the problems that face EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities. In this study, some of the items of the questionnaire were adopted from Mutlu (2014), Koross (2016), AL-Amiri (2018), AL-Darawish (2017), AL-Salkhi (2008), and Shaheen (2009), and then developed to suit the students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities. Some of the items of the questionnaire were designed based on the researchers' experience and the responses they got from other practicum students when they were asked about the problems they face during the practical education stage. The questionnaire consisted of six domains with (56) items. Five-point Likert scales ranging from high degree to very low degree was adopted.

Structured Interview

The Interview questions were constructed to measure the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities. The interview included open-ended questions to let the participants express their thoughts and ideas freely. The data collected was recorded in quiet places and then written down for data analysis.

The validity of the instruments

The questionnaire and the interview were handed to twelve well-qualified experts in the field. They evaluated the items of the questionnaire and the interview in terms of relevance, clarity, and relatedness to the research purposes. In response to their notes, suggestions, and feedback, some changes and improvements have been taken place. Pearson Correlation Coefficients showed that all items are significantly correlated with the total degrees (P-Values less than 0.05).

Reliability of the Questionnaire

The reliability coefficient for the domains of the questionnaire was 0.91 and this score is suitable for such types of studies.

The Correction key

To determine the degree of participants' responses, the following levels have been adopted: Very low (1.8), low (1.8-2.6), medium (2.6-3.4), high (3.4-4.2).

Results of the study

First question: What is the degree of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities?

The following table shows Means, Standard Deviations and Percentages for study domains.

Table 1. Means, standard deviations and degrees of all domains.

11	M	SD	Degree
The first domain: Problems related to the academic supervisors	3.02	0.77	Medium
The second domain: Problems related to the cooperative teacher	3.01	0.70	Medium
The third domain: Problems related to school students	3.05	0.60	Medium
The fourth domain: Problems related to the cooperative school	3.11	0.53	Medium
The fifth domain: Problems related to the student-teacher	3.11	0.64	Medium
The sixth domain: Problems related to the practicum program	3.25	0.64	Medium
The total Degree of problems	3.09	0.47	Medium

Table 1 shows that the total degree of the problems is medium. The total mean value is (3.09) with a medium degree. The sixth domain 'Problems related to the practicum program' was the highest with a mean of (3.25), while the lowest domain was the second one 'Problems related to the cooperative teacher' with mean of (3.01) scoring a medium degree.

Second question: Are there differences in arithmetic means among EFL students' responses regarding the problems they face in their practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender, cumulative average, and university?

To answer this question, the following null hypotheses have been investigated:

The first hypothesis (H01): There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender.

The following table shows the results of the T-test for independent samples. It shows the differences in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender:

Table 2. T-test results for the gender variable.

Domain	Gender	N	M	SD	T	DF	Sig.
Problems related to academic supervisors	Male	25	2.84	0.87	-1.270	140	0.206

	Female	117	3.06	0.75			
Problems related to the cooperative teacher	Male	25	2.87	0.73	-1.058	140	0.292
	Female	117	3.03	0.69			
Problems related to school students	Male	25	2.89	0.60	-1.443	140	0.151
	Female	117	3.08	0.59			
Problems related to the cooperative school	Male	25	2.95	0.54	-1.723	140	0.087
	Female	117	3.15	0.53			
Problems related to the student-teacher	Male	25	3.03	0.47	-0.742	140	0.459
	Female	117	3.13	0.67			
Problems related to the practicum program	Male	25	3.27	0.63	0.151	140	0.880
	Female	117	3.24	0.65			
Total Degree of Problems	Male	25	2.97	0.47	-1.437	140	0.153
	Female	117	3.11	0.46			

According to the results in table (1), the T-test for independent samples shows that there are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender.

The second hypothesis (H02): There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the cumulative average.

The researchers calculated means, standard deviations of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to cumulative average. To make sure if the differences in the mean scores were statistically significant or not, the researchers used the ANOVA test as seen in table (3) below.

Table 3. One Way ANOVA test results for the cumulative average variable

Domain	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F value	Sig.
problems related to the academic supervisors	Between Groups	6.214	3	2.071	3.689	0.014*
	Within Groups	77.497	138	0.562		
	Total	83.711	141			
Problems related to the cooperative	Between Groups	3.403	3	1.134	2.414	0.069
	Within Groups	64.852	138	0.470		

teacher	Total	68.255	141			
Problems related to school students	Between Groups	2.410	3	0.803	2.313	0.079
	Within Groups	47.924	138	0.347		
	Total	50.334	141			
Problems related to the cooperative school	Between Groups	2.663	3	0.888	3.287	0.023*
	Within Groups	37.272	138	0.270		
	Total	39.936	141			
Problems related to the student-teacher	Between Groups	6.284	3	2.095	5.556	0.001*
	Within Groups	52.024	138	0.377		
	Total	58.308	141			
Problems related to the practicum program	Between Groups	1.620	3	0.540	1.321	0.270
	Within Groups	56.395	138	0.409		
	Total	58.015	141			
Total Degree of Problems	Between Groups	2.706	3	0.902	4.445	0.005*
	Within Groups	28.010	138	0.203		
	Total	30.717	141			

* **Significant at 0.05 level.**

It can be concluded that there are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores due to the cumulative average for the domains 'problems related to the academic supervisors, Problems related to the cooperative school and Problems related to the student-teacher in addition to the total degree of the domains'. However, there are no statistically significant differences due to the cumulative average for the domains 'Problems related to the cooperative teacher, problems related to school students, and problems related to the practicum program'.

The third hypothesis (H03): There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the university.

First, the researcher calculated means and standard deviations of the respondents' responses regarding the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to university variable. To make sure whether the differences in the mean scores of the respondents' responses due to university variable are statistically significant or not, the researcher used the ANOVA test as seen in table (4) below.

Table 4. One Way ANOVA test for the university variable.

Domain	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F value	Sig.
problems related to the academic supervisors	Between Groups	8.751	4	2.188	3.998	0.004*
	Within Groups	74.960	137	0.547		
	Total	83.711	141			
Problems related to the cooperative teacher	Between Groups	3.479	4	0.870	1.840	0.125
	Within Groups	64.776	137	0.473		
	Total	68.255	141			
Problems related to school students	Between Groups	3.111	4	0.778	2.257	0.066
	Within Groups	47.222	137	0.345		
	Total	50.334	141			
Problems related to the cooperative school	Between Groups	2.419	4	0.605	2.208	0.071
	Within Groups	37.517	137	0.274		
	Total	39.936	141			
Problems related to the student-teacher	Between Groups	1.733	4	0.433	1.049	0.384
	Within Groups	56.574	137	0.413		
	Total	58.308	141			
Problems related to the practicum program	Between Groups	0.632	4	0.158	0.377	0.824
	Within Groups	57.382	137	0.419		
	Total	58.015	141			
Total Degree of Problems	Between Groups	1.863	4	0.466	2.211	0.071
	Within Groups	28.854	137	0.211		
	Total	30.717	141			

Significant at 0.05 level.

According to the results in table (4), there are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores due to the university variable for the domain ' problems related to the academic supervisors'. On the other hand, there are no statistically significant differences in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the university for the domains 'Problems related to the cooperative teacher, problems related to school students, problems related to the cooperative school, problems related to the student teacher, and problems related to the practicum program'.

Interview analysis

This section deals with the results of the 20 EFL interviewees' responses who have been taking practicum courses at Palestinian universities.

Que.1. How many times do the academic supervisors visit you?

70% of the subjects said that the academic supervisors visit them twice during the training period at schools. 30% of the respondents declared that they have been visited only once.

Que.2. Are you generally satisfied with the way according to which you are assessed?

Most of the interviewees were not satisfied with the way by which they were assessed. They stated that they need much more time and visits to be assessed appropriately. Most of the interviewees replied by saying 'it is unfair to be assessed in such a short time'.

Que.3. Starting from your placement at your cooperating schools, what difficulties have you experienced in the practicum programs?

Some student teachers said that the cooperative treated them arrogantly. The distance from their places of residence to the hosting school is also one of the problems they usually face. The most common answer by most of the respondents is the gap between what they have learned at universities and what they have experienced at schools.

Que.4. Do you think the practicum programs prepare you for actual teaching after you graduate?

They mentioned that theoretically they have been taught many courses on how actual teaching should be practiced in the field, but when it comes to reality, the issue is not so easy to practice. Most of them said that 'While at university, we believed that most of the learned theoretical issues are applicable, but when we entered schools facing real students with all difficulties accompanied by the teaching and learning process, we discovered that the mission was not as easy as we thought'.

Que.5. Do you have any suggestions for the improvement of the practicum programs? If you were to restart the programs, what changes would you like to see?

Some of them said that before going to schools supervisors should make sure that student teachers can give lessons, manage classes, plan lessons through assigning hands-on activities. They added that only through microteaching, they could gain self-confidence and be more able to manage in the practical education requirements. They also suggested that schools should have the necessary technological devices to enable students to apply what has been learned at universities.

Que.6. what qualities do you think the university supervisor should possess?

All of them agreed that the university supervisors should possess many characteristics such as being cooperative, knowledgeable, flexible, patient, impartial and more tolerant.

Que.7. what qualities do you think cooperating teachers should possess?

Cooperating teachers should be more sociable, patient, cooperative, and flexible. They also need to give more chances for the trainees to practice teaching.

Que.8. what professional competencies are teacher trainees expected to possess by the time they finish the practicum programs?

All of them expected that there are many professional competencies the teacher trainees should possess by the time they finish the practicum program training. They should be able to manage their classes, making lesson plans and dealing with large classes at schools. They are also expected to better understand the students' behaviors and use teaching strategies and methods that fit the students' levels, desires, abilities, and needs.

Que.9. Are there any comments that you would like to add?

Some students left no comments; others said they would like to decrease the number of reports required by the practical education file (the portfolio). They assured that these reports are a waste of time and the focus should be on the practical side not on writing reports. Some of them asked head teachers to give them more

chance to practice teaching others assured the fact that some cooperative teachers do not do their best to appropriately train the trainees.

Discussions, conclusions and recommendations

The results showed that the total degree of the problems that EFL students facing during their practicum courses at Palestinian universities is medium. This means that most students rate the problems they face in practicum courses nearly in the same way. But the issue is different regarding some items in some domains. For example, regarding the cooperative school domain, the two items (The limited number of cooperative schools lead to having many student teachers in the same school) and (Large classes in the cooperative school affect negatively the student teacher's ability to manage the classroom well) were in a high degree with means of (3.58) & (3.42) and standard deviation of (1.26) & (1.12). The researchers think that hosting schools play a crucial role in shaping the practical education program. Since there are a small number of schools, the universities oblige students to go to specific ones though they are far away from the students' place of residence. This may result in additional complications that lead to the failure of the whole process in some cases. The large classes are also one of the big problems that students face. The researchers believe that crowded classes play a significant role in hindering student teachers from doing their jobs properly. All trainees are novice teachers who lack planning, genuine methods of teaching, strategies for classroom management, etc.

From the student-teacher domain, two items scored high degrees which were (The student-teacher finds it difficult to coordinate between the practicum course and other courses in the same semester) and (The student teacher is frightened of supervisors' evaluation) with means of (3.63) & (3.41) respectively. The researchers think that it is time for universities to minimize the number of courses taken in the same semester of the practicum course. Since students are overloaded, they can't coordinate between these courses in a way that guarantees a kind of balance between the times dedicated for each of these courses. Student-teachers fear from the supervisor's evaluation is something odd as they should focus on the process as a whole and think how to get benefit from all stages of the practical education instead of thinking in grades. Nevertheless, a few of these fears are justifiable, as some of the supervisors evaluate students holistically depending on his impression without any criteria. This fear has been enhanced when some of the interviewees mentioned that some supervisors do not provide clear cut instructions and do not care about the problems the students face.

Although the total degree of the cooperative teacher's domain was medium, some students declared that the cooperative teachers deal with the trainees with pride and arrogance. They also added that the cooperative teacher doesn't have the necessary competencies, and he assigns to the student-teacher some duties that are irrelevant to the requirements of the practicum. This widens the gap between student teachers and cooperative teachers, and that worsens the situation. Such a fragile relationship won't lead to a fruitful practicum program. The relationship between trainees and cooperative teachers should be built on mutual understanding, respect and collaboration.

On the domain of the practicum program, three items scored the highest means (Lack of microteaching practice at universities before student teachers initiate their practicum at schools), (There is a gap between what has been learned at universities and the real environment at schools) & (The distribution of student teachers to schools doesn't take time into account the students' place of residence) with means of (3.78), (3.62) & (3.49) respectively. It is noticed that the respondent's responses to these three items were supported by the answers of the students to the questions of the interview. The harmony between student's responses to the questionnaire and that of the interview validate the results of this study. Responding to both tools, students emphasized the gap between the theoretical side and the practical side. They also mentioned that the distance between schools and their homes form a great problem for them. They also emphasize the importance of adopting microteaching at schools. The researcher believes that microteaching may result in bridging the gap between the course taken at universities and the practical side at schools. Students should be given authentic opportunities to practice teaching at universities before going schools.

Results also showed that there are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to gender in all study domains. The researchers attribute such a result to the fact that males and females live in the similar circumstances. They are studying at Palestinian universities in the same geographical area (West Bank). They

also came from the similar social background and being exposed nearly to the same curricula with slight differences. They also practice teaching at Palestinian schools that follow the rules and regulations.

There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the cumulative average according to: (problems related to the academic supervisors, problems related to the cooperative school, problems related to the student-teacher). The researchers think that these three partners are of paramount importance in the practicum program. On the other hand, the results showed that there are no statistically significant differences in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the cumulative average according to (Problems related to the cooperative teacher, problems related to school students, problems related to the practicum program), so the hypothesis H02 was accepted regarding these domains. Regarding problems related to the academic supervisors, the mean score for the Cumulative average group (80-89) is significantly higher than the mean score for the GPA group (60-69). Regarding problems related to the cooperative school and student-teacher, the mean score for the GPA group (80-89) is significantly higher than the mean score for the Cumulative average group (90 or more).

Results showed that there are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the university according to problems related to the academic supervisors, so the hypothesis H03 was rejected regarding this domain. On the other hand, results showed that there are no statistically significant differences in the mean scores of the problems facing EFL students in practicum courses at Palestinian universities due to the university according to problems related to the cooperative teacher, problems related to school students, Problems related to the cooperative school, problems related to the student teacher and problems related to the practicum program. So, the hypothesis H03 was accepted regarding these domains. The problems related to the academic supervisors, the mean score of An-Najah National University is significantly higher than the mean score of Bethlehem University.

Discussion of the Findings of the Interview.

As seen in the student's response to questions one, two and three, students emphasized the fact that one or two visits were not enough to evaluate students properly. This is in line with the questionnaire item that says (The academic supervisor doesn't provide developmental feedback on the student teacher's performance during the training process). The researchers attribute this shortage in developmental feedback to the pressure of time under which the academic supervisor works.

Regarding the cooperative teacher domain, the item (The cooperative teacher deals with the student trainee with pride and arrogance) was in harmony with the answers of some respondents to the interview question No. 9. Students showed their resentment from some cooperative teacher's behavior as they consider themselves superior to the trainees. The questionnaire item (The cooperative teacher doesn't allow the student teacher to teach more than one class daily) was in line with some of the student's responses to the questions of the questionnaire when they showed their wish to be given the chance to teach more than one period daily.

Respecting the domain of the school students, the item (Students don't interact actively in the lessons) was in agreement with some of the respondents' answers to the interview mainly in question 4 when some of them mentioned that students are so passive and rarely participate in lessons.

Regarding the domain of the cooperative school, the item (The cooperative school doesn't prepare a special training program for the student teachers that takes into consideration their circumstances and their training needs) was in line with the interview answer in which they suggested that schools should have the necessary technological devices to enable student teachers to apply in reality what they have learned at universities.

Concerning the domain of the student-teacher, most of the respondent's answers were in line with most of the items in that domain. Most students' responses highlighted the difficulties they face during the implementation of the whole program and more specifically when they are at the hosting schools. For example, they showed weakness in dealing with large classes, classroom management, dealing with teen's odd behaviors, involving and engaging students into lessons, etc.

Regarding the problems of the domain of the practicum program, the item (Lack of microteaching practice at universities before student teachers initiate their practicum at schools) agreed with the responses seen in

question 6 in which most of the student-teachers assured that before going to school and start the training program, they should have been given a good chance to practice teaching via microteaching in the universities. They added that only through microteaching, they could gain self-confidence and be more able to manage in the practical education requirements. The item (The distribution of student teachers to schools doesn't take time into account the students' place of residence) agreed with the responses of some students who assured that schools should not be far away from their places of residence. The item (There is a gap between what has been learned at universities and the real environment at schools) was in accordance with many responses in the interview in which we saw how student teachers were shocked when they went to the field as they have discovered the huge gap between what has been learned at the university and the real practice at schools.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. More visits should be assigned for the trainees to have a wider chance to practice their English language and more courses on practical education should be added to the practicum program.
2. Enhancing collaboration between the student-teacher and the hosting schools.
3. School administration should urge the cooperative teachers to offer more help and support to the trainees so that they can get the optimal benefit from the training course and Some changes in the practicum program should take place about its content. These courses should include more hands-on activities such as microteaching.
4. Further studies can be conducted to investigate problems that may face trainees in other disciplines at other Palestinian universities.

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